

1 Whole transcriptome profiling of an affinity isolated cell type from the blood during Plasmodium infection.

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8 Parasitic infection with Plasmodium species results in millions of Malaria disease cases in Africa and
9 worldwide. While Plasmodium falciparum infection and disease mechanisms has been more
10 comprehensively described, Plasmodium vivax is the largest contributor to Malaria infection. Here we
11 measured total transcription in affinity isolated CD71+ cells from bone marrow aspirates of 3 individuals
12 during acute infection with P. vivax and 48 hours following resolution of disease after administration of
13 treatment. Cells activated Erfe during acute infection and expressed CD69, Slamf7 and Slamf8, and
14 CD163. Cells produced TNF, IL1b, CCL3, CCR5, and CXCL2. Activation of inhibitory exhaustion and
15 tolerance receptors Fpr2 and Lag3 was observed. Cells activated markers of self indicated through class I
16 MHC receptors HLA-E, HLA-J, HLA-B, HLA-C and HLA-H and expressed cell surface redeptors Siglec9,
17 Siglec14, Ly6E, Flvcr2, Ms4a6a, Vsig4, and C-type lectin receptors Clec7a and Clec2b. P. vivax infection
18 activated the interferon system (MX1, GBP1, IFI6, IFI30, IRF1) and resulted in activation of injury
19 responses (TIMP, NINJ1, PTAFR). We described here basic elements of the transcriptional response to P
20 vivax parasite infection during acute infection *in vivo* in an isolated, defined cell type.

21 Citations

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24 Plasmodium falciparum) in vitro. The Journal of Experimental Medicine, 16(4), pp.567-579.

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